

NEWSLETTER

CONCILIARE: progressing with our journey!

Welcome to the seventh edition of our newsletter!

As 2026 begins, we are proud to reflect on CONCILIARE's recent achievements, as well as the many partnerships and activities developed to date. As we embark on a new year of work and commitment to confident change in cultural heritage, we wish you all great inspiration for the challenges ahead.

PUBLICATIONS

Visualising the Colonised Other: Representations of Identity and Power in Finnish Textbook Images

Inari Sakki and Aino Santavuori recently published an article in the *Journal of Community and Applied Social Psychology*, resulting from research within the framework of CONCILIARE's Working Package 1. The paper investigates how images related to colonialism in Finnish school textbooks construct identity and power. [Click here to read.](#)

Sakki, I., & Santavuori, A. (2026). Visualising the Colonised Other: Representations of Identity and Power in Finnish Textbook Images. *Journal of Community and Applied Social Psychology*, e70219. <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.70219>

PAST EVENTS

International Workshop - Textbooks and Voices in Contemporary Europe

Last December, the workshop hosted by the University of Coimbra on behalf of the CONCILIARE project brought an opportunity to share expertise and perspectives on history education and representations of the colonial past in textbooks. Together, the participants exchanged knowledge towards creating a pedagogical tool to improve decolonial education in schools.

Collective memory and the transmission of cultural knowledge

From 1 to 7 December, Laurent Licata visited the University of Lubumbashi, Democratic Republic of Congo, where he presented the CONCILIARE project to a Congolese audience. The presentation was part of the scientific workshop “Collective memory and the transmission of cultural knowledge”, within the project called “Towards psychosocial reappropriation and resocialisation by the source communities of Katanga of the remains of ancestors to be repatriated and cultural objects to be recovered”, funded by ARES.

Discovering Lisbon's African Heritage

Members of the CONCIARE project participated in a decolonial tour in Lisbon, Portugal, conducted by Djuzé Neves and called "Discovering Lisbon's African Heritage". This is an initiative developed by the Batoto Yetu Portugal Association, which aims to disseminate the city's African heritage, usually scattered in a variety of visible and invisible memories and traces today.

The activity was a partnership between CES and Batoto Yetu, and shows how populations such as Moors, Muslim Africans, Arabs, and others have been a structural element of Portuguese urban life for a long time.

Discussing the decolonisation of CCH with PhD students at the University of Coimbra

On 19 December, three researchers from our project gave a lecture on "Decolonisation of CCH in Portuguese cities" to students in the Doctoral Program on Sociology – Cities and Urban Cultures at the Faculty of Economics of the University of Coimbra. Sebastián Zuñiga, Júlia Vilhena and Pedro Menezes shared the theoretical and methodological framework of CONCIARE and debated the results of research conducted so far in Lisbon, Porto and Lagos.

The session provided an inspiring discussion with PhD students on the modes of understanding the presence of colonial heritage in urban public space and on the

sociological, political and civic challenges emerging from the ongoing processes of epistemic decolonization of Portuguese history and collective memories.

CONCILIARE IN THE MEDIA

- Yasmina Zian, from our ULB team, was interviewed by the national French-speaking media (RTBF) on the changes at the MRAC (Musée royal de l'Afrique centrale) and highlighted some results from our report on changes in the museum (WP3). [Click here](#) to read the full article.
- Sheila Khan, a researcher from our CECS team, regularly participates in the radio show "Debate Africano" by RDP Africa. In December, she mentioned and valued the CONCILIARE project in the episode dedicated to 2025 year-end review. [Click here to watch.](#)

UPCOMING EVENTS

CONCILIARE's annual meeting

In a few days, Brussels will be the meeting point for our members to reconnect, integrate and share results and experiences over the last year. Our second annual meeting will be held from January 28 to 31, at the ULB campus - Solbosch Campus, Building S, Somville Room.

The event will happen simultaneously with the International Conference "Colonial Legacies in Belgium", organised in partnership with the ARC-HERICOL research project (GERME, AGS, LAMC). To check the full conference program and register to attend, [click here](#). So, get ready and we'll see you there!

Colloquium Rethink Latin America - Decoloniality, Interculturality, and New Subjectivities

The 2nd International Colloquium "Rethink Latin America" will take place from February 25 to 27 at the University of Minho, in Braga. With the central theme "Decoloniality, Interculturality, and New Subjectivities" the event aims to reflect on the diverse ways of existing, expressing, and resisting that emerge in response to the

